

Reactive Methylene Compounds. Part X. Behaviour with some Polynitrohalogenobenzenes

H. G. Garg*

Behaviour of several polynitrohalogenobenzenes with reactive methylene compounds has been investigated and characteristics of the derivatives are described.

The relative reactivity of the (-CH₂-) in reactive methylene compounds usually depends on the character of the attached electronegative groups. With a view to subjecting the above postulate to experimental verification the condensation of a number of methylene compounds with polynitrohalogenobenzenes has been investigated.

In 1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone and 1-(4-nitrophenyl)-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone, the hydrogen atom of the methylene group at 4-position is very reactive, so much so, that they react with 1-bromo-2, 4-dinitrobenzene in ethanolic solution containing sodium acetate and yield the substituted derivative (cf. Rowe and Twitchett, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1704). The various compounds, thus prepared, are described in Table I and II.

(R = Phenyl or substituted phenyl)

1-Bromo-2, 4-dinitrobenzene did not however react with indane-1, 3-dione, methone, benzoylacetones, acetoacetic esters, or diethyl malonate under these conditions; sodium salts of these had to be prepared which reacted with 1-bromo-2,4-dinitrobenzene to afford the corresponding dinitrophenyl derivatives.

*Present address: Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow.

In the case of benzoylacetate ester or dibenzoylmethane even the sodium salt did not react smoothly (cf. Borsche, *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 601) and the potassium salts had to be prepared which yielded the required dinitrophenyl derivatives (cf. Gambhir, Ph.D. Thesis, *Agri Univ.*, 1956).

EXPERIMENTAL*

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (Knorr, *Ber.*, 1883, **16**, 2597), 1-(4-nitrophenyl)-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (Altschul, *Ber.*, 1892, **25**, 1853), indane-1, 3-dione (Teeters and Shriener, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 3027), methone (Vörländer, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1929, **77**, 245) and benzoylacetones (Garg, this *Journal*, 1961, **38**, 113) were prepared by known methods.

Reactive halogen compounds were obtained either by nitration of the corresponding halogenobenzenes or by treatment of polynitrophenols with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in diethylaniline.

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-5-pyrazolone.—1-Bromo-2,4-dinitrobenzene (0.01-M) was added to a boiling solution of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (0.01-M) in ethanol (100c.c.) containing sodium acetate (8 g.). The mixture was refluxed for 4 hours and then diluted with water. The crude product after recrystallisation from a mixture of ethanol and acetic acid furnished a crystalline compound.

By adopting a similar procedure other substituted pyrazolones from 1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones and 1-(4-nitrophenyl)-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones were prepared; their characteristics are given in Table I and II respectively.

TABLE I

No.	4-Substituted-1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone	Yield	M.P.	Colour	Formula	Found	Calc.
1.	4-(2,4-Dinitrophenyl)-	82%	216°	Orange	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₅ N ₄	N : 16.24	16.47
2.	4-(3-Chloro-4, 6-dinitrophenyl)-	70	236°	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClO ₅ N ₄	Cl : 9.32	9.48
3.	4-(3-Methyl-4, 6-dinitrophenyl)-	48	215°	"	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₅ N ₄	N : 15.67	15.81
4.	4-(2-chloro-4, 6-dinitrophenyl)-	58	218°	Orange	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₅ ClN ₄	Cl : 9.28	9.47
5.	4-(2-Bromo-4, 6-dinitrophenyl)-	58	216°	"	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₅ BrN ₄	Br : 18.89	19.09
6.	4-(2,6-Dinitro-4-bromophenyl)-	49	220°	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₅ BrN ₄	Br : 18.92	19.09
7.	4-(3,5-Dibromo-2, 4-dinitrophenyl)-	49	202°	"	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₅ Br ₂ N ₄	Br : 32.34	32.12
8.	4-(2,4,6-Trinitro-3-methylphenyl)	46	252°	Dark brown	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₇ N ₅	N : 17.41	17.54
9.	4-(2,4,6-Trinitrophenyl)-	51	220°	Brown	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₇ N ₅	N : 18.01	18.18

TABLE II

No.	4-Substituted-1-(4-nitrophenyl)-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone.	Yield	M.P.	Colour	Formula	Found	Calc.
1.	4-(2,4-Dinitrophenyl)-	80%	285°	Chocolate	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₇	N : 18.02	18.18
2.	4-(3-Chloro-4, 6-dinitrophenyl)-	74	261°	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClN ₅ O ₇	Cl : 8.58	8.46
3.	4-(3-Methyl-4, 6-dinitrophenyl)-	40	259°	"	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₇	N : 17.41	17.54
4.	4-(2-Chloro-4, 6-dinitrophenyl)-	60	221°	Brown	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClN ₅ O ₇	Cl : 8.31	8.46
5.	4-(2-Bromo-4, 6-dinitrophenyl)-	61	226°	"	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ BrN ₅ O ₇	Br : 17.14	17.24
6.	4-(2,6-Dinitro-4-bromophenyl)-	52	248°	Blackish brown	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ BrN ₅ O ₇	Br : 17.14	17.24
7.	4-(3-Methyl-2,4,6-trinitrophenyl)-	42	Above 300°	Dark brown	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₆ O ₉	N : 18.78	18.91
8.	4-(2,4,6-Trinitrophenyl)-	53	Above 300°	"	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₆ O ₉	N : 19.48	19.53
9.	4-(3,5-Dibromo-2,4-dinitrophenyl)-	49	226°	Brown	C ₁₆ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₅ O ₇	Br : 29.21	29.46

*Melting points are uncorrected.

2-(2,4-Dinitrophenyl)-indane-1,3-dione.—A suspension of the monosodium derivative of indane-1,3-dione (0.05-*M*) in ethanol (15c.c.) and 1-bromo-2, 4-dinitrobenzene (0.05 *M*) were refluxed for 5 hours and filtered. The filtrate was acidified with acetic acid and allowed to stand. A gummy product separating after treatment with activated charcoal gave a crystalline product from acetic acid.

By adopting a similar procedure derivatives from methone and benzoylacetones were prepared. Characteristics are summarized in Table III.

TABLE III

No.	2,4-Dinitrophenyl-derivative of	Yield	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1.	Indane-1,3-dione	58%	242°	Yellow	C ₁₅ H ₈ O ₆ N ₂	N : 8.68	8.97
2.	Methone	60	254°	Light yellow	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₂	N : 9.07	9.15
3.	4-Chlorobenzoylacetone	46	138°	Colourless	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₆ ClN ₂	Cl : 9.61	9.79
4.	4-Bromobenzoylacetone	45	168°	Colourless	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₆ BrN ₂	Br : 19.51	19.65
5.	4-Methylbenzoylacetone	34	112°	Pale yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₂	N : 7.98	8.18
6.	4-Methoxybenzoylacetone	31	118°	Pale yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₂	N : 8.01	7.82
7.	3,4-Dichlorobenzoylacetone	40	136°	Pale yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₆ Cl ₂ N ₂	Cl : 17.61	17.88
8.	2-Chloro-5-methyl benzoylacetone	39	122°	Colourless	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₆ ClN ₂	Cl : 9.21	9.42

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
MEERUT COLLEGE,
MEERUT.

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